

Advancing Green Supply Chain Practices in B2C E-Commerce

B. Shreepathy Ranga Bhatta¹, Dasharathraj K. Shetty^{2*}, Lewlyn L.R. Rodrigues³ and Sandeep S. Shenoy³

1. Manipal Academy of Higher Education (MAHE), Department of Humanities and Management, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal - 576 104, Karnataka, India
2. Manipal Academy of Higher Education (MAHE), Department of Data Science and Computer Applications, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal - 576 104, Karnataka, India
3. Manipal Academy of Higher Education (MAHE), Department of Commerce, Manipal - 576 104, Karnataka, India

*Corresponding author, Email: raja.shetty@manipal.edu; shreepathy.b@learner.manipal.edu

Business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce prioritizes green supply chain practices (GSCP) to improve environmental sustainability and meet demand for green products. Even with advances, a deep awareness of the research landscape and prospects for the future is needed. This study examines B2C e-commerce green supply chain practices using a comprehensive literature review and criteria for inclusion and exclusion. The findings highlight green supply chain tactics, including ethical procurement, environmentally friendly operations and eco-friendly packaging, which lower carbon footprints and boost market standing. However, these projects face organizational, financial, technological and regulatory obstacles. Looking ahead, stakeholder participation, multidisciplinary approaches, policy ramifications and research methodology improvements are needed to sustain the sector. According to the analysis, green supply chain practices in B2C e-commerce have a bright future for sustainability and corporate success. Future explorations should innovate methods and engage diverse stakeholders to increase green supply chain uptake.

KEYWORDS

B2C e-commerce, Sustainability, Green supply chain, Research agenda

1. INTRODUCTION

Business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce has swiftly developed in the age of digital transformation and has taken the lead among all other forms of retail globally [1]. However, this development has led to greater environmental concerns because of expansion of logistical activities, packaging waste, carbon emissions and other environmental issues [2-5]. As result, scholars and practitioners have started discussing application of green supply chain practices (GSCP) in B2C e-commerce [6]. These actions seek to reduce detrimental environmental effects of corporate operations while also perhaps bringing about positive economic and social effects [7-9]. Although there has been a lot of research on green supply chain management (GSCM), there aren't many studies that particularly examine its use and effects in the B2C e-commerce sector [10,11]. Additionally, studies already conducted have mostly emphasized advantages of GSCP, paying less attention to the difficulties and obstacles that organizations

encounter in putting these into practice, which resulted in contradicting conclusions about its effectiveness [12,13]. This review aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive overview of GSCP in B2C e-commerce, including strategies, impact, challenges and emerging trends.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This extensive literature study included clear research goals and questions. A comprehensive search string meticulously identified relevant articles from several databases using predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Articles on GSCP in B2C e-commerce must be in english and peer-reviewed. Non-english, peer-reviewed or e-commerce papers unrelated to GSCP were excluded. This ensured a targeted, trustworthy evaluation of the most relevant and reputable sources.

2.1. Theoretical framework

2.1.1 Green supply chain management theories and principles: Incorporating environmental concerns into all aspects of supply chain operations, such as product design, material sourcing, manufacturing, product distribution and end-of-life management, is known as

Table 1. Description related to various themes studied in the paper

Aspect/theme	Description	Reference
Procurement and supplier selection		
Lifecycle assessment	Stressing the necessity of lifetime environmental impact assessment	[39]
Supplier selection and evaluation	Discussing sustainable supplier selection and evaluation methods	[94,95]
Buyer-supplier relationships	Examining sustainable buyer-supplier relationships	[95,96]
Sales channel strategies	Optimization of sales channels based on customer pricing sensitivities	[97]
Environmental and social factors	Stressing social and environmental concerns in sustainable procurement	[96]
Technological approaches	Selection of suppliers and evaluation using technology and innovation	[94]
Consumer sensitivities	Supplier and platform selection strategies should consider consumer preferences and sensitivities	[97]
Eco-friendly packaging and materials		
Sustainable design solutions	Package designs using recyclable and 3D-printed materials	[5]
Consumer preferences	Examining economic and normative factors for eco-friendly packaging preferences	[42]
Challenges and risks	Reusing and sustainable packaging implementation obstacles and hazards	[41]
Case studies and models	Case studies to propose and demonstrate sustainable packaging development models	[43]
Innovative technologies	Highlighting how emerging technologies promote sustainable packaging and energy savings	[39]
Regulations and policies	Discuss how legislation and policies, like the European green deal, promote sustainable packaging	[5,41]
Consumer motivations	Examining consumer incentives and how they affect eco-friendly packaging	[42]
Energy-efficient warehousing and inventory management		
Automation and robotics	Promote warehouse automation and robotics for efficiency and faster decision-making	[48,59,98]
Innovative frameworks and architectures	Innovative smart warehouse systems and reference designs for personalized inventory control and customized needs	[48,59,98]
Sustainable inventory management	Address sustainable surplus inventory management, including disposal decisions balancing financial and non-financial concerns and health and environmental risk	[49]
Technological enhancements	Discuss the importance of real-time management of stocks and IT integration in e-commerce logistics	[48,59,98]
Future research directions	Creative and customized warehouse management solutions and practical use of new technology are promising research fields	[48,59,98]

GSCM [14]. This strategy is based on theories, like stakeholder theory, which emphasizes organization’s duty to environmental stewardship for a variety of stakeholders and natural resource-based view (NRBV), which emphasizes an organization’s responsibility to protect natural resources [15].

2.1.2 Environmental sustainability in e-commerce: The B2C e-commerce sector, which is expanding rapidly provides wide reach and constant accessibility. Still, it raises serious environmental issues, such as increased

packaging waste energy use and carbon emissions, primarily because of logistical operations [16-23]. The adoption of digital goods and services, which lessen the need for physical infrastructure and the use of data analytics to improve logistics and cut emissions, however, hold potential to boost environmental sustainability [23-28].

2.1.3 Integrating green supply chain practices and e-commerce research: E-commerce needs GSCM principles to be sustainable [29]. This integration must ad-

dress environmental impacts across the supply chain from product sourcing, packaging, warehousing, transportation, delivery and reverse logistics management [10,13]. There are a few GSCM and e-commerce merger research, underlining a crucial gap and the need for more specialized research [10,13,30-32]. Summing up, GSCP in B2C e-commerce research, this paper attempts to close this gap and enhance the constantly expanding sector.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Sustainable procurement and supplier selection

Sustainable procurement is one of the core tenets of GSCM and it entails choosing suppliers based on their environmental performance in addition to price and quality [19]. According to Zhu *et al.* (2013), Yen (2018) and Melandar (2018), supplier participation and collaboration are crucial for accomplishing environmental goals [33-35]. Businesses increasingly include sustainability criteria in selecting their suppliers [36,37]. One example is the use of life-cycle assessment tools to gauge the environmental impact of a supplier's products (Table 1) [38,39].

3.2 Eco-friendly packaging and materials

An important step towards going green in B2C e-commerce is adoption of eco-friendly packaging materials [5,21,41]. Research show businesses are switching to recyclable, biodegradable, or reusable packaging to reduce waste [42,43]. Some businesses are also improving and innovating with the materials they use in their packaging designs while maintaining product protection (Table 1) [39,44].

3.3 Energy-efficient warehousing and inventory management

Warehousing and inventory management are important components of the e-commerce supply chain that have a big impact on the environment [45]. Studies have shown that integrating energy-efficient technology and practices in warehouses can dramatically cut energy usage [41,46,57]. Similarly, effective inventory management techniques can reduce overstocking and the associated waste [48-50].

3.4 Sustainable transportation and last-mile delivery

The carbon footprint of e-commerce logistics can be greatly reduced by using sustainable transportation tactics, such as route optimization and usage of electric vehicles [4,21,51,52]. To further boost efficiency and

cut emissions, businesses are now investigating cutting-edge last-mile delivery options including drone deliveries and pickup locations (Table 2) [52,53].

3.5 Reverse logistics and product return management

E-commerce has a big problem with product returns significantly impacting the environment [54-56]. Reverse logistics techniques and effective procedures, such as centralized return centers and refurbishing and resaling returned goods, can lessen these effects (Table 2) [57-59].

3.6 Waste reduction, recycling and end-of-life product management

To reduce the environmental impact of e-commerce operations, waste reduction and recycling measures, such as take-back programmes for old goods and packaging, are essential [60-62]. To manage the end-of-life of their products, some businesses are also deliberating on extended producer responsibility (EPR) methods (Table 2) [62].

3.7 Consumer engagement and education

The effectiveness of green practices depends on consumer engagement [63-65]. Companies employ a variety of tactics to encourage consumers to adopt sustainable behaviours, such as informing customers about the environmental impact of items and enticing them to recycle their used goods [66,67]. Several businesses are also utilizing gamification and reward systems to encourage environment friendly behaviours [68,69].

3.8 Outcomes and implications of green supply chain practices

GSC practices produce a range of benefits, including improvements in environment, economy, society and competitive posture. Key performance indicators including lower carbon emissions and higher recycling rates, which translate to better sustainable profiles for businesses are ways to measure environmental improvements [8,23,24,70,71]. Economically, despite the high initial expenses, adopting GSC can result in long-term financial gains due to increased productivity and government incentives, preventing potential fines and promoting cost savings down the road [72-76]. The societal impact of GSC practices is significant, improving the perception of stakeholders by promoting possibilities in the green economy, bettering health and safety standards and enhancing public perception [30,77-80]. These effects also manifest in higher ratings from the clients and greater appeal to potential employees. Busi-

Table 2. Description related to various themes studied in the paper

Aspect/theme	Description	Reference
Sustainable transportation and last mile delivery		
A green vehicle integration	Discussions and assessments of integrating EV's and drones into urban logistics to reduce environmental consequences. This encompasses the argument over urban green car economic and environmental viability, governance and technological incentive policy	[23,51,53,99]
Economic and environmental assessment	Studies compare the last-mile delivery vehicles' environmental and financial outcomes, including electric and internal combustion engine cars. These discuss modern sustainable technology's pros and cons	[51,52,99]
Consumer perceptions and receptivity	Studies of consumer attitudes and behaviors towards upcoming delivery technology like drone services, emphasize privacy and unfamiliarity	[52]
Innovative solutions and future directions	Comprehensive evaluations of current creative solutions and future trends in last-mile delivery transport, focusing on phases of development, features and difficulties of modern systems like automation stations and drone transportation	[53]
Collaborative approaches and CSR	Focus on multi-stakeholder collaboration to improve urban logistics sustainability and efficiency, emphasizing CSR's role in meeting changing expectations and regulations	[55]
Reverse logistics and product return management		
Return less refund policies	Return-less refund policies' pros and cons, including net sales increases and return fraud	[99]
Sustainable business models	Develop sustainable business concepts to address increased product returns using a multidisciplinary approach	[54]
Pricing and quantity optimization	Optimization of the price and item quantities for handling high return rates requires more study on efficient algorithms for varied market conditions	[55]
Supply chain paradigms	New paradigms for efficient return handling in demand uncertainty scenarios, focused on SC cooperation and return handling costs	[56]
Second-hand market strategies	Analysis of online second-hand market operational tactics, business styles and e-trading platform owners	[57]
Reverse logistics networks	Emphasis on building strong reverse logistics network for packing surplus and using AI techniques to improve return flows	[58]
Waste reduction, recycling and end-of-life product management		
Consumer preferences on overpackaging	Consumer attitudes about overpackaging, emphasizing recycling and regulation over combo packing	[60]
Reuse of packaging materials through reverse logistics	Explore sustainable e-commerce packaging reuse through enhanced infrastructures and collaborations	[61]
Extended producer responsibility	Discussing how EPR promotes trash diversion, reuse and recycle internationally and calling for producer accountability	[62]
Value stream mapping (VSM) in supply chain	Investigation of using VSM to detect and decrease waste in retailer-to-consumer distribution to improve customer happiness and cut expenses	[100]
Impact on urban pollution	Study of China's 'National E-commerce Demonstration Cities policy' shows reduced pollution and boosted e-commerce in sustainable urban development	[101]

Table 3. Description related to various themes studied in the paper

Aspect/theme	Description	References
Consumer engagement and education		
Consumer preference for green logistics	Examine consumers' growing propensity to judge products according to their environmental impact, quality and performance	[63,102, 103]
GSCM strategies	Investigate the best practices for GSCM to improve society's sustainability, quality and general well-being	[67]
Role of gamification in e-commerce	A thorough examination of psychological factors that contribute to effectiveness of gamification in improving client retention in online retailers	[68]
Incentives for sustainable shopping	Assess nudging tactics to promote sustainable online shopping and emphasize the need to match incentives to context	[102]
Green clothing market opportunities	Emphasize environmental education's importance in retailers' ability to capitalize on consumers' willingness to buy eco-friendly clothing and using AI techniques to improve return flows	[103]
Impacts of green supply chain management practices in e-commerce		
Return less refund policies	Return-less refund policies' pros and cons, including net sales increases and return fraud	[99]
Benefits of GSCMP	Examine the benefits of using GSCM practices from an economic and environmental standpoint	[8,29,104, 105,106]
Customer preferences and green innovation	Concentrate on knowing client preferences and fostering green innovation to increase the demand for and profitability of green products	[66,107,108]
Technological advancements in GSCM	Using technology to support GSCM and advance environmental protection	[104,109]
Policy and practice insights	Exploring ways to use e-commerce to improve environmental sustainability	[106]
Emerging trends and promising innovations in e-commerce supply chain		
Blockchain in e-commerce	Examines the PRODCHAIN blockchain's possibilities for transparent product tracing in upcoming supply chains	[92]
5G and IoT	Effectively and profitably agricultural products may be sold online utilizing 5G IoT technologies	[93]
Big data	How data algorithms and mining models are being developed to improve customer relationship management and digital marketing techniques	[110,111]
Forecasting in logistics	Focuses on the advantages of a cooperative technology approach for improving forecast accuracy and stock control in markets	[112]
IoT-driven logistics	Leverages IT solutions like GPS and IoT for better position tracking and network optimization to concentrate on optimizing last-mile delivery	[115]
ICT trends in omni-channel logistics	Examines how various ICT systems, such as network extensions and real-time inventory monitoring, might improve logistics management	[114]

nesses utilising GSC techniques gain a competitive advantage by satisfying the growing demand for green products and establishing a distinctive market standing through innovation and enhanced product quality (Table 3) [98-84].

3.9 Challenges and barriers to green supply chain adoption

Organizational, financial, technological and regulatory challenges must be overcome to implement GSCP. Organizations struggle with managerial challenges, such

as potential change resistance and the lack of a clear sustainability plan, which impede a smooth transition to GSC operations [85-87]. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are particularly affected by financial barriers since they frequently must deal with high initial expenses and unpredictable financial situations, making it difficult to get green investments and financing [88-91]. Along with physical gaps in the logistics and transportation sectors, technological shortcomings also present a difficulty because current technologies are insufficient for monitoring and mitigating environ-

mental effects [92]. The regulatory environment is also a mixed bag; while strict environmental regulations can encourage green initiatives, their presence and inconsistent application, as well as complex international regulations, may make it difficult to implement GSC strategies. This highlights a market with a variety of compliance requirements and complex incentive structures [73-75,79,93].

3.10 Emerging trends and promising innovations

Industry 4.0 and technological trends are transforming GSCM by improving productivity, transparency and ecological impact mitigation with blockchain and AI [86]. Collaborative consumption, sharing, leasing and encouraging second-hand markets, reduce waste and extend product life in the circular economy [87]. Smart transport and logistics technologies have also transformed e-commerce's environmental impact by using autopilots, drones and robots for last-mile deliveries and real-time tracking for operational efficacy and transparency [86]. A shift in consumer behaviour towards sustainable consumption has prompted companies to provide comprehensive ecological impact information about their products and offer eco-friendly alternatives, promoting GSCP in business (Table 3) [30,35,60,64].

3.11 Research agenda and future directions

Though GSCP in B2C e-commerce has improved, research gaps exist and offer opportunities for future research, such as how new technology and consumer behaviour affect GSC adoption and sustainable business models. To better comprehend SCM, e-commerce and sustainability in environment, theoretical advances and interdisciplinary approaches from the economic, social and environmental realms are needed. Using big data analysis and AI may be crucial and longitudinal research could illuminate GSCPs' changing landscape and long-term effects. A deeper understanding of policy implications and stakeholder interaction, including customers, vendors and policymakers, will help create effective rules and promote GSCM.

4. CONCLUSION

GSCM is needed to address sustainability issues, including carbon emissions and packaging waste, as B2C e-commerce grows worldwide. This comprehensive review addresses a research gap in B2C e-commerce by examining the benefits and practical problems of GSCM adoption. It highlights the need for approaches and innovations that cover every stage of the supply chain, including sustainable buying, sustainable packaging and energy-efficient warehouses, to promote environmen-

tal sustainability, economic viability and social acceptance. Critical analysis of environment friendly transit and last-mile delivery and the rise of reverse logistics and product management for returns are also covered. It identifies waste reduction, end-of-life product management and consumer interaction and education as key to GSCP. Despite organizational and technological limits, emerging trends like 5G IoT for quality control and big data for logistic optimization are paving the way for growth. Future studies should examine how evolving technology and changing consumer behaviours affect GSC practices, using multidisciplinary strategy to get comprehensive insights. It suggests promoting stakeholder interaction for policymaking, promising a more sustainable and greener B2C e-commerce future.

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